

Prognostic Factors in Survival of Patients With Stage Ta and T1 Bladder Urothelial Tumors

The Role of G₁-S Modulators (p53, p21Waf1, p27Kip1, Cyclin D1, and Cyclin D3), Proliferation Index, and Clinicopathologic Parameters

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Abstract

We studied 159 cases of superficial (stage Ta or T1) bladder tumors to determine the significance on survival of a subset of regulators of transition from G₁ to S phase of the cell cycle (p53, p21Waf1, p27Kip1, cyclin D1, cyclin D3) and tumor proliferation (Ki-67 [MIB-1]). Clinical findings (patient age, sex, tumor size, grade, stage [Ta or T1]) were included in the analysis. Univariate analysis revealed association of tumor size (P = .0353), grade (P = .0182), and Ki-67 index (P = .0033) with disease-free survival and of tumor size (P = .0005), stage (P = .0494), cyclin D3 expression (P = .0105), and Ki-67 index (P = .0272) with overall survival. Cox multivariate analysis revealed cyclin D1 expression and high proliferation index (disease-free) and tumor size, cyclin D3 expression, and high proliferation index (overall survival) as independent predictors. Results suggest that alterations of the progression from the G₁ to S phase of the cell cycle are common in papillary urothelial bladder tumors. High tumor proliferation, expression of cyclins D1 and D3, and tumor size at diagnosis might be relevant predictors of survival in patients with stage Ta and T1 bladder urothelial tumors.

At diagnosis, most bladder tumors are superficial (stage Ta or T1); 70% of them are papillary noninvasive (stage Ta), and the remaining 30% manifests with early stromal invasion (stage T1).^{1,2} Following initial transurethral resection of the bladder tumor, patients at risk for recurrence or progression can be identified by a variety of prognostic factors, including tumor grade, the depth of bladder wall invasion, the presence of vascular or lymphatic invasion and early recurrence, the number and size of tumors, and the finding of concomitant dysplasia or carcinoma *in situ*.^{1,3-6} However, it has been recognized that these prognostic factors are not sufficiently accurate to predict true biologic behavior⁷; therefore, more reliable indicators of biologic aggressiveness are needed in stage Ta and T1 bladder tumors.⁷

In these tumors, although studies on prognostic biologic markers are limited, a number of cell cycle aberrations have been studied in an attempt to identify tumors prone to progress, but most reports show variable and somewhat contradictory results.⁷⁻¹⁰ Tumor proliferation is considered a powerful prognostic indicator of tumor recurrence, and p53 nuclear accumulation is viewed as a marker of progression in superficial bladder tumors¹¹⁻¹⁵; but some studies failed to demonstrate any independent prognostic significance in patients with superficial bladder tumors.¹⁶⁻²¹ Data concerning other G₁-S modulators such as p21Waf1, p27Kip1, and cyclin D1 are limited.^{8,9,18,21-28} and alterations of cyclin D3, another upstream regulator of the cell cycle, have not been reported in bladder cancer.^{29,30} Nevertheless, it has been suggested that alterations of cell cycle regulatory proteins involved in the progression from G₁ to S phase are among the most promising markers,²⁹ and their role in the prognosis of superficial bladder tumors needs to be established.

The purpose of our study was to determine the predictive value of the expression of the G₁-S modulators p53, p21Waf1, p27Kip1, cyclin D1, and cyclin D3 and of cell proliferation as measured by the Ki-67 (MIB-1) labeling index in the survival of patients with primary Ta and T1 bladder cancer. Patient age and sex, tumor size, pathologic stage, and grade also entered the analysis as clinical and pathologic variables.

Materials and Methods

Patients and Clinical Follow-up

A sequential cohort series of 159 patients with primary bladder tumors who underwent complete transurethral resection of bladder and random bladder biopsies was the study group. Resection of primary tumors was performed by 6 staff urologists, and the patients were seen at Reina Sofia University Hospital, Córdoba, Spain, between January 1990 and December 1995. Patients diagnosed as having high-grade bladder carcinoma additionally received intravesical instillation of bacille Calmette-Guérin (Olgason, West Orange, NJ). The strain, 2.5 × 10⁸ colony-forming units weekly for 6 consecutive weeks, starting 10-15 days after transurethral resection of bladder) with no maintenance as the current protocol in clinical practice.

Patient follow-up, calculated as the number of months from the date of the diagnostic surgical procedure to the date of the most recent cystoscopy (or to the date of the last visit or death), was 5 to 12 years (mean ± SD, 74.8 ± 28.1 months; range, 6-120 months).

Tumor recurrence was defined as reappearance of tumor after the initial treatment, with at least 1 tumor-free cystoscopy in the interval. Survival time was defined as the period between the time of diagnosis and the time of death. Cancer-related death was defined as that caused by bladder carcinoma. The end point of the study was disease-free and overall cancer-specific survival. Preoperative excretory urography was performed to exclude causes with evidence of upper urinary tract disease, and tumor size was defined as the largest tumor measured with the

resection loop that is, 1 cm long; thus, patients were stratified as having tumors of less than 3 cm, 3 to 5 cm, and more than 5 cm. All available H&E-stained slides, including primary tumors and recurrences, were reevaluated by 3 dedicated pathologists (A.L.B., R.J.L., and A.Q.) without knowledge of the clinical status and were graded in accordance with the 2004 World Health Organization (WHO) classification (former WHO/International Society of Urological Pathology, 1988).^{5,6} Clinical and pathologic staging was determined in accordance with the 2002 TNM revision.³¹

Immunohistochemical Analysis

A representative paraffin-embedded specimen was selected from each tumor based on the amount of neoplastic tissue present. Then, blocks were cut serially at 4 μm thick, deparaffinized in xylene, rehydrated in graded ethanol, and washed for 5 minutes with phosphate-buffered saline. For antigen retrieval, the sections were boiled immersed in a 10-mmol/L concentration of citrate buffer (pH 6.0). Endogenous peroxidase was blocked by incubation of the slides for 30 minutes with 3% hydrogen peroxide in methanol. Sections then were incubated with primary mouse monoclonal antibodies at room temperature (Table 1). Immunohistochemical stains were performed using a highly sensitive, polymer-based detection system (EnVision, DAKO, Glostrup, Denmark) for 30 minutes at room temperature. Diaminobenzidine substrate solution (0.6 mg/mL in dihydroxyethylamine-hydrochloride-buffered saline, pH 7.6 with 12 mL of 30% hydrogen peroxide) was used as a chromogen. Sections were counterstained with Mayer hematoxylin, dehydrated, and mounted using a standard procedure. Appropriate controls, positive and negative (replacing the primary antibody with distilled water), were included (Table 1).

Evaluation

The quantitative and qualitative assessment of the immunohistochemical study was conducted using a Nikon Labophot optical microscope (Tokyo, Japan). Three dedicated pathologists (A.L.B., R.J.L., and A.Q.) independently evaluated all immunohistochemical slides in a blinded manner without knowledge of clinical information. The same area on each slide

Table 1. Characteristics of Immunohistochemical Markers

Marker	Clone*	Source	Working Dilution	Positive Control Sample	Incubation Time (min)
Cyclin D1	DCS-6	DAKO, Glostrup, Denmark	1:25	Mammary cell lymphoma	60
Cyclin D3	DCS-22	DAKO	1:25	Breast carcinoma	60
Ki-67	MIB-1	Concoga Biosystems, Barcelona, Spain	Precluded	Tonsil	60
p21Waf1/Cip1	SX118	DAKO	1:25	Breast carcinoma	45
p27Kip1	SX5358	DAKO	1:25	Colon adenocarcinoma	45
p53	PA01801	Novocastra, Newcastle upon Tyne, England	1:40	Breast carcinoma	60

* All were mouse monoclonal antibodies.

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